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REPORT

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1 Executive Summary

Supporting bio-based products has been recognised by the EC as an essential element towards circularity. Moreover, research has shown that product design determines up to 80% of a product's lifecycle environmental impact. However, where the EU policy framework in the last decade has been significantly expanded and strengthened, it currently does not include requirements directly targeted at promotion of bio-based polymers.

This report provides an overview of the recent legislative requirements and policies defined at EU level. Most of the recent policies are defined in the framework of the new EU Circular Economy Action Plan, including the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation. This proposed regulation takes the 2009 Ecodesign Directive further by defining ecodesign requirements for producers on the end-of-life of the products they produce. Compared to the existing Directive, the proposal adds more product groups and strengthens the requirements.

While these ecodesign requirements indirectly stimulate the use of bio-based materials and products, there is limited direct stimulation for the production or consumption of such bio-based materials and products while this is needed to achieve full circularity. This report therefore explores options to strengthen the current policy framework in that direction and to add additional policies to provide more direct stimulation of production of bio-based products. For this, inspiration is taken from other recent policies, such as the policy framework for bio-based plastics and biodegradable or compostable plastics. Further inspiration is taken from the chemicals strategy for sustainability, that takes existing regulations on chemical substances forward by adding an explicit aim to boost innovation in industry for safe and sustainable-by-design chemicals, including sustainable bio-based chemicals.

A strong element of the entire policy framework is that it combines measures to support more sustainability on the production side with measures to strengthen the position of consumers with regards to sustainability as well as to direct financial support towards sustainability. To strengthen the position of consumers the Commission proposed a directive on empowering consumers for the green transition, a directive on green claims and a directive on the right to repair. This report provides a short summary of the new proposals as well as suggestions to strengthen the requirements that could enhance the market for bio-based products. One of the proposals to direct financial support towards sustainability is the EU Taxonomy, which is a transparency tool and classification system that helps direct investments to the economic activities most needed for the transition towards the EU's 2050 decarbonisation target.

The review of the existing policy framework leads to a series of recommendations of which the most prominent are:

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1. Define minimum sustainability targets that are legally enshrined and sector-specific.
2. Formulation of targets and ecodesign requirements should be incremental, achievable and with a longer-term horizon.
3. Take a wider geographic perspective when defining targets and ecodesign requirements.
4. Formulate mandatory ecodesign requirements for specific products.
5. Define more specific quality standards to support sustainability.
6. Improve the definition of circular economy in corporate sustainability reporting and require reporting in line with targets and standards.

2 Introduction

The CHAMPION project aims at developing novel, fully bio-based polymers that are circular by design, i.e. recyclable back to bio-based monomers, and/or that are biodegradable. These polymers are more sustainable and safer alternatives to fossil-based polymers and are suitable for a circular approach to coatings, homecare products and structural adhesives. These could be an important building block in the transition of the EU economy towards circularity. To support such a transition, the European Commission (EC) has formulated various regulations and supporting policies.

Until 2018 the leading EU policy in this area was the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, which was first launched in 2012 and updated in 2018. With an overall goal defined as “the partial replacement of non-renewable products by more sustainable biobased ones”, the EU Bioeconomy Strategy included 14 specific actions to strengthen and scale up bio-based sectors. In a stocktaking report issued in 2022, the EC concluded that the actions had led to an increasing number of national and regional bioeconomy strategies and an increased mobilisation of private and public investments and research and innovations in bio-based industries (European Commission, 2022d). Yet it also concluded that more action was needed. Specifically, that “a stronger leverage for bio-based materials and products must create an even playing field on the market”.

Other European policies have a more direct impact on the market for bio-based products, with requirements specified either on the use of biomass or on biomass waste as input for biopolymer production. With respect to the use of biomass, the regulation with most impact is the Renewable Energy Directive (European Commission, 2023c), that defines sustainability and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions saving criteria for biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels. For use of waste streams, there are various regulations that set restrictions on shipment of waste, such as the Regulation on the Shipment of Waste and the Basel Convention. Furthermore there are various directives and regulations that define criteria on chemical substances, such as REACH (see further information in section 6.1) and the Classification, labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation (see further information in section 6.2).

In the last decade, the focus of policy attention was to bring circularity much more to the forefront of EU industrial policy. This was taken further in the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), and related regulations (see further information in section 3.2 and chapter 4). Among other measures this resulted in strengthening of the ecodesign and energy labelling measures for several products, which now include rules on material efficiency requirements such as availability of spare parts, ease of repair, and facilitating end-of-life treatment. While this indirectly stimulates the use of bio-based materials and products, achieving circularity actually needs to address the beginning of a product's life: the design phase and then the production processes, including the product sourcing. Regulation, however, still stays limited in the aspect of sustainability of bio-based materials at the level of design and should set more firm criteria in order to direct consumption towards bio-based products.

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This report discusses some of the recent regulations and policies and explores how they could be further detailed, complemented or adapted from the perspective of stimulating the demand for, use of or production of bio-based materials and products. Initial results of analysis and recommendations have been discussed in focus group meetings, to ensure views of a wider group of stakeholders are taken into account. Chapter 3 of this report discusses the current regulations supporting the EU ambition to further develop and strengthen a circular economy. Chapter 4 further expands on the new Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP II) focusing on some of the proposed policy packages.

A fundamental step to ensure that the EU sustainability goals are met is that it is financially supported and investments are directed towards sustainable activities. Chapter 5 discusses how the EU is currently addressing this. It also includes the EU Taxonomy, that defines criteria to define what activities can be considered sustainable. Chapter 6 explores the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, which is relevant to stimulate the market for bio-based polymers. Finally, chapter 7 provides an overview and summary of the policy recommendations that were provided throughout the report.

3 Striving towards a European circular economy

This chapter discusses the EU ambitions for a circular economy and the existing regulatory framework to support that ambition.

3.1 EU ambitions for a circular economy

In December 2019 the EC presented the Green Deal for the European Union (EU) and its citizens. This European Green Deal is one of the 6 EC priorities defined by the EC for the period 2019-2024. The Green Deal is the EC's response to the challenges of climate change and environmental-related challenges such as the warming of the atmosphere, a strong reduction of biodiversity on earth and pollution of oceans. The Green Deal presents a strategy that aims to transform the EU economy into one that is resource-efficient with net zero GHG emissions in 2050. One of the key elements of the Green Deal is mobilising the European industry for a clean and circular economy, as is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The European Green Deal (Source: European Commission, 2019)

When the Green Deal was presented, the EC envisaged developing at relatively short notice a new EU industrial strategy (European Commission, 2023) and a new circular economy action plan (CEAP) to support the circular design of products. The previous, first, CEAP was adopted in

December 2015 and delivered 54 specific actions report by March 2019 (European Commission, 2019a, see more detail in section 3.2).

Supporting bio-based products has been recognised by the EC as an essential element towards circularity. In 2013, the Commission Expert Group for Biobased Products was set up to advise the EC on the development of the bio-based products sector. Their final report, published in 2017, contains 9 guiding principles and 8 policy recommendations for jobs and growth through bio-based products. One recommendation is to coordinate bioeconomy within the overall EU policy framework, through a full revision of the bioeconomy strategy, enabling the sustainability assessment of (bio-based) products and the application of standards and labels to allow better evaluation by purchasers. The 8 policy recommendations were consecutively addressed in a range of EU policies and strategies such as the update of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy in 2018 and its corresponding action plan, the progress report and the actions of the progress report published in 2022, and the various research and innovation activities under the Horizon program.

Also, in the EU Green Deal industrial plan, as formulated in the communication of 1 February 2023, bio-based products are defined as a priority area to reduce material use (European Commission, 2023). In this plan, and earlier strategies, bio-based substitutes are also identified as promising options to enhance economic growth and lower the dependence on fossil fuels. All plans and strategies identify bio-based products and the bio-based industry as an essential enabler to achieving circularity, which provides high potential for future growth and addressing societal challenges. However, no specific targets are set in terms of the share of bio-based products in the EU economy or on promoting use of bio-based polymers.

Several regulations and policies exist that indirectly influence the position of bio-based polymers or products vis-à-vis their less sustainable alternatives. The next section summarises the main elements of the existing regulatory framework, after which we zoom in on specific recent and proposed policies, with an analysis how these could support the market for bio-based polymers and explores options for additional support.

3.2 The existing EU regulatory framework

As mentioned in the previous section, one of the most prominent existing EU regulations to support the transitioning of the EU's economy to full circularity is the CEAP. The CEAP, adopted in December 2015, was the first EU-wide strategic document that promotes a systemic approach to achieve circularity across entire value chains. It does so by mainstreaming circular principles into plastic production and consumption, water management, food systems and the management of specific waste streams.

In addition to supporting circularity, the CEAP also included specific ambitions to create new jobs, support economic growth and investments. In 2018, the EU Monitoring Framework for the Circular Economy was developed that specified 10 indicators that cover competitiveness aspects

as well as each phase of the lifecycle of products (European Commission, 2018). Based on this monitoring framework, the EC concluded in their 2019 report on the implementation of the CEAP, that these ambitions have been achieved (European Commission, 2019a).

One of the most prominent actions put forward by the CEAP is the EU Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (European Commission, 2018a), which is the first EU-wide policy framework adopting a material-specific lifecycle approach, aiming for all plastic packaging placed on the EU market to be reusable or recyclable by 2030.¹ It includes a target that by 2030 55% of plastic packaging should be recycled. The CEAP also includes the Single Use Plastics (SUP) Directive (European Commission, 2019b) that bans single use products made of plastic and products made from oxo-degradable plastic from the European market.

Taking the CHAMPION ambition to develop bio-based polymers that are circular by design, the Plastics Strategy provides interesting inspiration, among which:

1. One of the specific objectives of the Plastics Strategy is to ensure that, by 2030, all plastics packaging placed on the EU market is reusable or easily recycled. While not specifically targeting plastics, CHAMPION's ambitions in general go much further as it is not just focusing on reuse and recycling, but on achieving full circularity by ensuring that polymers are circular by design. For packaging this could, for example, be achieved when a plastic coating on paper packaging would be produced with bio-based polymers. Specific target setting would help the industry to shift its focus along these lines, for the plastics sector as well as for other sectors. Yet, the possibilities and timeline for achieving full circularity differs per sector. It is therefore recommended to make agreements to reaching circularity at sectoral level, taking into account the product- and sector-specific challenges and following the waste hierarchy. Having such targets agreed will support the market for bio-based polymers.
2. The Plastics Strategy identifies that the lack of information regarding the possible presence of chemicals of concern (e.g. flame retardants) creates a significant obstacle to achieving higher recycling rates in the automotive, furniture and electronics sectors. These sectors are identified as important applications for plastics use and a significant source of plastics waste that could be recycled. The Strategy therefore includes the ambition to accelerate work to identify possible ways to make chemicals easier to trace in recycled streams. This has a close relation to two of the main areas of application targeted by CHAMPION: Car interior surfaces and coatings. Easier tracing of chemicals in recycled streams could result in a higher market interest for alternative products made from CHAMPION polymers that are non-chemical and easier to recycle.

¹ While the CHAMPION project does not specifically target plastics, the bio-based polymers it aims to create would provide a sustainable and safer alternative to fossil-based polymers, including some conventional plastics. It is however not this application that is analysed here, but the policies that are defined for plastics are used as inspiration for further policies to support the market for bio-based polymers.

3. The Plastics Strategy also identifies that weak demand for recycled plastics is a major obstacle to transforming the plastics value chain, given uncertainty concerning market outlets and profitability. One measure taken up by the EC to address this obstacle is to develop quality standards for sorted plastic waste and recycled plastics, in cooperation with industry. This would deliver the standardisation of quality specifications and therewith help scaling up. The obstacles identified are not only valid for recycled plastics but are also common to many of the markets for recycled products and green innovations, including for the targeted applications of CHAMPION products. It would help CHAMPION products if standardisation is developed for other recycled product groups or more generally for bio-based and recycled polymers. The criteria used by technical standards and certification schemes in relation to the use of recycled content should support bio-based products that were manufactured with post-consumer bio-based plastic waste, preferably with no downcycling. Also, standards and certification schemes used to make claims on biodegradability and compostability of bio-based materials and products should further define their criteria to clearly inform if they apply to the whole product or which specific parts of it. The information about the conditions under which the used bio-based materials and products will be accepted at a composting facility, and the time needed for degradability and compostability, should be fully transparent and accessible to consumers. In general, regulation should require companies to substantiate their claims with life cycle analysis and without overlooking circularity aspects including examining all end-of-life options; even littering.

The CEAP implementation report concluded that more of these sector-specific strategies would be needed for many other sectors with high environmental impact and potential for circularity such as information technologies, electronics, mobility, the built environment, mining, furniture, food and drinks or textiles. Furthermore, this report concluded that life-cycle assessments of products should become a norm and the eco-design framework should be broadened as much as possible. These, and other recommendations, were addressed in CEAP II (see also Chapter 4) that was adopted in March 2020 (European Commission, 2020).

Some of the other main, relevant regulations are the EU Waste Framework Directive (WFD) and the formulation of EU standards for industrial composting and biodegradation. The WFD was adopted in 2008, with a further specification published in 2011 and an amendment adopted in 2019. Its main requirement is that loss of material after a product's service life should be prevented and further processing and handling of waste is required, following the waste hierarchy. Provisions apply regardless of material origin and regardless of its degradability profile. The EU standards include requirements on disintegration and biodegradation of products. For example, standard EN 13432 requires for packaging at least 90% disintegration after 12 weeks and 90% biodegradation in 6 months.

Again, these elements of the EU regulatory framework do not include requirements directly targeted at promotion of bio-based polymers. The WFD does provide an indirect support to

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bio-based polymers when produced from biowaste within the meaning of the WFD. Producers could obtain an End-of-Waste (EoW) status for these polymers, based on which regulations for further processing and handling as prescribed by the WFD no longer have to be followed.

4 The new EU Circular Economy Action Plan

The new CEAP (CEAP II) was presented by the EC on 11 March 2020 and, after scrutiny by the European Council and European Parliament, it was adopted on 17 December 2020. CEAP II builds on the actions implemented as a result of CEAP I. Section 4.1 provides a short description of the CEAP II and some of its proposed actions. The sections thereafter provide an analysis of these proposed actions, including identifying policy gaps and providing recommendations on how to address these gaps in relation promotion of the market for bio-based products or polymers.

4.1 Ambitions of the CEAP II and the policy packages proposed

The CEAP II proposes a list of 35 legislative and non-legislative measures along the entire life cycle of products. The set of measures targets how products are designed, promotes circular economy processes, encourages sustainable consumption, and aims to ensure that waste is prevented with the resources kept in the EU economy for as long as possible. Specific actions are proposed for electronics and ICT; batteries and vehicles; packaging; plastics; textiles; construction and buildings; and food.

The specific measures are proposed in packages. At the time of completing this report (January 2024), three of such packages have been proposed:

1. The first package of proposals was presented in March 2022. This package includes, a proposal for the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR, see more detail in section 4.2), an EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles, and a proposed directive on empowering consumers in the green transition (see more detail in section 4.3).
2. The second package, presented in November 2022, includes a proposal for a revision of the EU legislation on packaging and packaging waste, an EU policy framework on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics (see more detail in section 4.4), and a proposal for a regulation on EU certification for carbon removals.
3. The third package was presented on 22 March 2023 and includes a proposal for a directive on substantiation and communication of explicit environmental claims ('green claims directive') and a proposal for a directive on common rules promoting the repair of goods.

In addition, on 15 May 2023, the EC published a revised circular economy monitoring framework, aimed at better tracking progress in the transition to a circular economy in the EU.

In the following sections some of the main proposed actions are elaborated and it is explored to what extent they could help promote the market for bio-based products or polymers.

4.2 Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation

Research has shown that product design determines up to 80% of a product's lifecycle environmental impact.² Therefore, in 2009, the EC adopted the Ecodesign Directive, covering energy related products. To extend the range of products covered, and to broaden the scope of the requirements with which products are to comply, the EC published on 30 March 2022 the proposal for the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR – European Commission, 2022a). The ESPR sets new requirements to make products more durable, reliable, reusable, upgradable, repairable, easier to maintain, refurbish and recycle, and energy and resource efficient. In addition, product-specific information requirements will ensure consumers know the environmental impacts of their purchases. All regulated products will have Digital Product Passports, which will make it easier to repair or recycle products and facilitate tracking substances of concern along the supply chain.

The proposed ESPR is a framework regulation that empowers the EC to adopt delegated acts that establish specific ecodesign requirements for products to improve their environmental sustainability. The type of design requirements proposed to be formulated under ESPR delegated acts will require deconstruction of materials into separable components and materials. However, if the remaining components are not fully biodegradable, or if such components are a mix of biodegradable and non-biodegradable polymers, these requirements are not sufficient to facilitate circularity. To reach that goal, the product design requirements should facilitate deconstruction down to the molecular level, i.e. polymers and their constituent monomers.

To enhance the uptake of design requirements by industry it could be useful to explore adding mandatory recyclability requirements to the policy package. Such requirements are also proposed for textiles, in the targeted revision of the Waste Framework Directive (European Commission, 2023b). In particular, the targeted revision proposes mandatory and harmonised Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes for textiles in all EU Member States. Similar mandatory recyclability requirements could be added for other products or product groups for which recycling options are commercially available. Furthermore, it would be useful to include biodegradability in the ESPR ecodesign requirements, again tailored to the particular characteristics of the product or product groups concerned. To ensure consistency between EU regulations, the requirements would need to be formulated based on existing EN standards where possible. Existing standards at a material level could be adapted to the component level, where possible, or additional standards could be defined.

Whereas the CEAP II specifically mentions the aim to “stimulate the development of lead markets for climate-neutral and sustainable products”, the measures included in the ESPR, do not include much certainty for the industry that a market for their innovation in sustainable products will actually develop and therewith a high risk on their investments. Therefore, it seems useful to

² European Commission, 2014.

include some target setting, such as on the share of recyclability. To help industry to gradually adapt to requirements it would be recommended to use incremental target setting, alongside a final target defined for the medium or longer-term. Such target setting will also provide a further boost to business models of biopolymer producers and industries ready to replace part of their materials with sustainable alternatives. To make such target setting effective, a system of compliance and enforcement would need to be implemented, with penalties for non-compliance in the form of, for example, a fine or revoking the license to operate.

Since the production costs of biopolymers are still significantly higher than for their fossil-based alternatives, a form of financial incentive could be considered to help the market take off and reach a certain level of maturity. In the early years, subsidies or tax breaks could be used that help producers meeting ESPR requirements. Such support should be in line with the State aid Guidelines for climate, environmental protection and energy, have a clear end date and be limited to covering the cost difference between non-sustainable products currently sold and their ESPR-compliant alternatives.

Finally, in light of competition on the global market it is important to ensure a level playing field for actors within the EU and external to the EU. A further strengthening of the ecodesign requirements, especially in case of the introduction of mandatory targets, would likely result in a cost increase for EU-based producers. The level playing field could be achieved by introducing taxation on products entering the EU market that do not meeting ESPR requirements. A precedent to this exists on the European carbon market, with the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (European Commission 2023h). This regulation will add a price on the embedded carbon emissions of products imported to the EU from 2026. This mechanism was defined to avoid carbon leakage and encourage partner countries to establish similar carbon pricing as applied in the EU.

4.3 The directive on empowering consumers

In addition to the Ecodesign regulation, there are three further proposals to strengthen the position of consumers. Two of these were proposed as part of the third package: the directive proposals on green claims (European Commission, 2023f), and the right to repair (European Commission, 2023g). Already part of the second package of the CEAP II is the directive on empowering consumers for the green transition, which was proposed by the EC on 30 March 2022. The proposal aims at enhancing consumers' rights by amending the unfair commercial practices directive (UCPD) and the consumer rights directive (CRD) and adapting them for the green transition. On 19 September 2023 a provisional agreement was reached between the Council and the Parliament and adoption is expected soon.

The Directive on empowering consumers requires that consumers must be informed about the durability and reparability of products. To do so it requires that environmental and social impact,

durability and repairability will be added to the list of product characteristics about which traders are forbidden to mislead consumers (Article 6 UCPD). Furthermore, traders providing a service that compares sustainability of products would be required to disclose information on the method of comparison to avoid misleading of consumers (Article 7 UCPD). The list of banned commercial practices (Annex I UCPD) is extended to avoid so-called greenwashing. Practices that are banned include displaying a sustainability label that is not based on a certification scheme or not established by public authorities, and false claims about durability or repairability of a product. Finally, the Directive includes requirements on informing consumers on the repairability score, if that exists under EU law, and on provide information that facilitates repair or when product durability is guaranteed longer than the two-year legal guarantee.

During consultation, many comments were focused on the stringency of requirements to ban green claims and the credibility of sustainability labels. In particular, consumer organisations asked for a ban on unverified climate neutrality claims. Some of these comments were addressed by the Council and the Parliament in their provisional agreement, including by defining the key elements of certification schemes, by banning claims on environmental impact based on unverified offsetting programs, and by introducing a harmonised label with information on the commercial guarantee of durability with a reference to the legal guarantee of conformity. In addition, the transparency and monitoring of claims related to future environmental performance has been increased. While these are steps in the positive direction, policymakers, manufacturers and certification schemes could do more to make environmental claims more credible and increase their transparency. Policymakers could, for example, continue pushing for the standardisation of terminology, symbols and metrics and enforce their use broadly to contribute to transparency. Manufacturers of bio-based products could source feedstock and bio-based materials from responsible hubs or from certified providers that have a transparent track record of good environmental practices. In this direction, certification schemes could improve their governance and establish a “Standard of Transparency” to inform consumers and to show which labels are most relevant to support which claims.

The Directive currently focuses on claims related to climate change, such as claims of carbon neutrality. For the next steps, it is advisable to also extend the ban of unverified claims to cover additional sustainability topics. For instance, bans on unverified claims on circularity, biodegradability, recyclability, and reusability could also be included. This would increase the trust that consumers have in a broader number of sustainability claims, especially if supported by reliable and transparent certification. This is important because studies show that the more consumers are aware of how certification works, the more they trust it, and the higher is their willingness to pay for the extra price of certified products (Panico et al., 2022; Richartz et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2023).

As soon as the Directive is adopted Member States have a maximum of 24 months to transpose the directive.

4.4 Policy framework for bio-based plastics and biodegradable or compostable plastics

Another one of the 35 actions proposed under the CEAP II is the policy framework for bio-based plastics and bio-degradable or compostable plastics. Whereas other proposed policies provide an indirect reference to bio-based production, or could indirectly impact the market for bio-based products or polymers, this policy will likely have a more direct impact.

The roadmap to the policy framework on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics was published by the EC in September 2021. After consultations, the framework was published on 30 November 2022 by means of a Communication (European Commission, 2022f). The Communication provides clarifications on bio-based, bio-degradable and compostable plastics and sets out the conditions to ensure that the overall environmental impact of their production and consumption is positive. However, it does not introduce legally binding requirements. The only legal requirements impacting the market for bioplastics are the Directive on single-use plastics (European Commission, 2019b), and the Directive on plastic bags (European Commission, 2015).

The Communication on the policy framework defines bio-based plastics as plastics made from biomass as opposed to fossil resources. Biomass encompasses plants (e.g. sugarcane) as well as organic waste and by-products (e.g. used cooking oil). Since producing primary biomass often results in negative environmental impacts, the framework prioritises the use of organic waste and by-products. Moreover, when primary biomass is used, it needs to be environmentally sustainable. The EC also states that biomass must comply with the sustainability requirements defined in Article 29 of the Renewable Energy Directives (European Commission, 2023c). Although this is a first step to guarantee feedstock sustainability, no directive specifically targets biomass used for bio-based plastics.

Furthermore, when assessing the sustainability of a product, it is fundamental to account for the impacts throughout its entire life-cycle. While the policy framework emphasises feedstock sustainability, it lacks a comprehensive overview on how to tackle the environmental impacts associated with the rest of bioplastics life-cycle. As the communication on the policy framework also highlights, methodologies to assess the life-cycle environmental impacts of bio-based plastics compared to fossil-based ones are still under development. Scientific literature carrying out similar comparisons often does not cover enough environmental impact categories, especially those related to land-use change (Bischof et al, 2021). The analysis is also complicated by the existence of many types of bioplastics, each with different characteristics and potential negative impacts (Sameh Samir Ali et al, 2023). It would therefore be useful for future policies to better understand the life-cycle environmental impacts of bioplastics when compared to fossil ones. For this, the development and testing of solid assessment methods are also necessary.

Another aspect to consider for inclusion in future policies is the requirement for a mandatory minimum bio-based content before a product can be defined as bio-based. The current policy framework explains that bioplastics can be fully or partially made from bio-based feedstock, but no specification is given on a minimum bio-based content. The EC takes steps to protect the consumers from misleading sustainability claims, for instance with the EC's proposal on empowering consumers for the green transition (European Commission, 2022e). Still, the policy framework would benefit from clearer guidelines on the bio-based content of products. This would also force further investigation as to which point different bio-based materials perform better than the fossil counterpart in terms of environmental impacts.

End-of-life options also need to be considered when determining the environmental impacts of products. In this sense, the policy framework poses great attention to how to correctly use biodegradable and compostable plastics. First of all, biodegradation cannot be used as a solution to inappropriate waste management or littering. Moreover, the use of plastics that biodegrade in the open environment must be limited to specific cases where their full degradation is proven to be possible, and for scenarios where reduction or reuse is not feasible. The framework also recognises that incentivising the use of biodegradable plastics risks slowing down the development of more circular options, and the investments in designing products with the intention of allowing their recycle and reuse.

Furthermore, a solid and reliable system needs to be in place to corroborate the sustainability claims made on a product. Sustainability certification can be a useful instrument in this sense, since the products need to comply with the sustainability requirements in order to obtain the certificate. Certification can also be applied to the entire value chain, enabling the origin of the materials to be traced and guaranteeing that every processing step respected the certification standards. It is also an easy instrument to empower consumers towards more sustainable choices. If certification is made visible on the end product, for instance by the presence of a label, consumers can immediately be assured that the product respects specific sustainability criteria.

4.5 The monitoring framework for the circular economy

In January 2018, the EC adopted the [EU monitoring framework](#) for the circular economy. The goal was to track and monitor the progress of the EU towards circular economy objectives. In May 2023, the framework was updated (European Commission, 2023d), to better align with the circular economy priorities outlined in the European Green Deal, the 8th Environment Action Programme, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the EU's objectives related to security of supply and resilience.

The monitoring framework comprises 11 indicators grouped into 5 categories:

1. Production and consumption: decoupling economic growth and resource use, as well as reducing waste generation are fundamental steps towards a circular economy. This

category uses material consumption and waste generation as indicators to measure progress towards these objectives.

2. Waste management: increasing recycling is part of the transition to a circular economy. For this, overall recycling rates and recycling rates for specific waste streams (e.g. plastic packaging) are monitored.
3. Secondary raw materials: in a circular economy, recycled raw materials are generally preferred to primary ones. This category measures the contribution of recycled materials to raw materials demand and the trade in recyclable raw materials.
4. Competitiveness and innovation: the indicators in this category monitor private investments, jobs and gross value added related to circular economy sectors, as well as innovation (i.e. patents).
5. Global sustainability and resilience: consumption in the EU causes impacts globally. A circular economy can limit these impacts and contribute to carbon neutrality. The indicators “global sustainability from circular economy” and “resilience from circular economy” are used to measure progress in this direction.

Replacing fossil-based materials with bio-based ones can significantly contribute to many of these objectives. For instance, the use of feedstocks obtained from recycled goods or by-products of other production streams can incentivise recycling practices and reduce the use of primary resources. However, especially when biomass is used as feedstock, it is important to also account for the negative environmental impacts that might arise. In particular, the monitoring framework lacks comprehensive considerations on agricultural practises. Sustainable farming methods, land use, and biodiversity considerations are integral to the circularity of bio-based feedstocks but are not adequately captured in the existing metrics.

Social considerations are another aspect that is not sufficiently tackled in the framework. A circular economy should increase peoples' access to goods and services, create new business models, engage communities, enhance environmental health, promote equity and inclusivity, and much more. The only social indicator monitored in the framework is employment in the recycling, repair and reuse, and lease and rental sectors. This approach is limited, as it does not encompass many other aspects that are relevant for a circular economy.

In general, the framework exhibits a narrow perspective when considering the circular economy. The gaze is very much focused on waste generation and recycling, overlooking other important circularity objectives. There is little or no mention of aspects like waste avoidance, extending the life of products, design for repairability and durability, transition to renewable resources, the shift from ownership to access, regeneration of biotic and abiotic resources, and so on (Vural Gursel et al., 2023). Although often difficult to measure and monitor, such consideration would broaden the scope of the framework and enable for a more comprehensive assessment of the progress towards a circular economy.

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Moreover, even though there are indicators covering resource use, they mainly refer to solid materials that go into products (biomass, metal ores, non-metallic minerals and fossil energy materials/carriers). The framework does not currently take into account the other types of resources used during the design, production, consumption, and final treatment of products. These include land, water, air, energy, bio resources, as well as human resources. Recognizing and quantifying these elements is a fundamental step to design and strengthen the circular economy.

5 Directing capital towards sustainable investment

Another key element in achieving the climate and energy targets as defined in the EU Green Deal is a sustainable finance strategy and enabling framework that directs investments in the European market towards sustainable projects and activities. To achieve this, the EC had already in October 2016 established the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on sustainable finance, requesting them to provide strategic recommendations for a financial system that supports sustainable investments. The HLEG published their recommendations in January 2018, which alongside other inputs formed the basis of the Action Plan on Financing Sustainable growth and led to the development of a classification system, or 'taxonomy', to provide market clarity on what is deemed 'sustainable'.

5.1 The Action Plan on Financing Sustainable Growth

On 8 March 2018 the Commission published a communication that is referred to as the 'Action Plan on Financing Sustainable Growth'. In this communication the Commission set out measures to further connect finance with sustainability. The main aims of the action plan are to improve information available for financial markets to provide investors with more information on which activities are sustainable, and thus align financial markets with EU sustainability goals. Or in more specific terms: to direct more funding to environmentally sustainable activities, particularly towards activities that are needed to reach the EU's 2050 climate neutrality targets. The plan includes ten key actions that are divided into three categories.

The first category aims at reorienting capital flows towards a more sustainable economy: this includes various actions. Firstly, establishing a comprehensive EU taxonomy (see section 5.2). The goal of the taxonomy is to provide a detailed and clear system to identify sustainable economic activities. In parallel, efforts include the development of an EU Green Bond Standard and the labels for green financial products, aiming to build confidence in sustainable finance products. Additionally, the EC is extending the EU Ecolabel framework to encompass minimum environmental performance criteria for retail financial products, to enhance their transparency and sustainability. To boost investment in sustainable projects, the plan involves connecting sustainable finance frameworks and tools with relevant EU funds. Finally, rules are being developed to guide the incorporation of sustainability considerations into financial advice, to make sure that these principles are integrated into financial decision making.

The second category focuses on enhancing and mainstreaming sustainability integration into risk management practices. One action is to better integrate sustainability considerations in credit ratings and market research, for instance by updating the guidelines on disclosure requirements for credit ratings by the European Securities and Markets Authorities. Another action was laid down in the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) which was adopted in December 2019. This regulation sets out how financial market participants have to disclose sustainability

information, aiming to help investors to make informed choices on sustainability aspects and understand how sustainability risks are integrated in the investment decision process. A final element in this category is the European Banking Authority (EBA) who was mandated to introduce a 'green supporting factor' in the EU prudential rules for banks and insurance companies. This was implemented in an Action Plan on Sustainable Finance published by the EBA in December 2019.

The goal of the last category is to foster transparency and long-termism. This involves strengthening sustainability disclosure and accounting rule-making, as evidenced by the update of the Non-Financial Reporting Directive to the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, as outlined in section 5.3. Lastly, efforts are made to promote sustainable corporate governance and mitigate short-termism in capital markets. Research in this domain leads to a recommendation to strengthen the disclosure of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors, facilitating institutional investor engagement in the pursuit of a more sustainable financial landscape.

5.2 The EU Taxonomy

The EU Taxonomy was defined to create security for investors, protect private investors from greenwashing, help companies become more climate-friendly and mitigate market fragmentation. This section discusses the regulatory framework and explores its potential impacts for the market for bio-based materials and products.

The EU Taxonomy regulation was published in the Official Journal on 22 June 2020 and entered into force on 12 July 2020 (European Commission, 2020b). It is a classification system that defines criteria for economic activities that are aligned with the EU's trajectory to achieve net zero GHG emissions by 2050 and the broader environmental goals other than climate. Larger companies, as well as small and medium-sized undertakings which are public-interest entities,³ are obliged to report in their annual reports to what extent their activities are covered by the EU Taxonomy (Taxonomy-eligibility) and comply with the criteria set in the Taxonomy delegated acts (Taxonomy-alignment). Other companies can disclose this information on a voluntary basis.

Companies need to report on six climate and environmental objectives against four overarching conditions that an economic activity has to meet in order to qualify as environmentally sustainable. The six climate and environmental objectives are: 1) Climate change mitigation, 2) Climate change adaptation, 3) The sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, 4) The transition to a circular economy, 5) Pollution prevention and control, 6) The protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems. The four overarching conditions that need to be met are:

1. Making a substantial contribution to at least one environmental objective;

³ Companies that are obliged to report are identified in the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (European Commission, 2022c).

able to be deemed as environmentally sustainable under the Taxonomy Regulation. These conditions are:

- 1) Their GHG emission levels correspond to the best performance in the sector or industry.
- 2) They must not hamper the development and deployment of low-carbon alternatives.
- 3) They must not lead to a lock-in of carbon-intensive assets considering the economic lifetime of those assets.
- 4) The technical screening criteria for these activities will need to ensure that these transition activities have a credible path towards climate-neutrality. To ensure this, technical screening criteria should be adjusted accordingly at regular intervals.

Both the production of bioplastics and organic basic chemicals are listed as "transitional activities". Bioplastics are deemed sustainable when meeting two criteria: i) when partially or wholly derived from a renewable feedstock(s) that comply with the sustainability criteria laid down in Article 29 of the Renewable Energy Directive, and ii) when the LCA-based GHG emissions are lower than that of the equivalent plastics in primary form manufactured from a fossil fuel feedstock. Similar requirements are defined for the production of organic basic chemicals. In particular, the GHG emissions derived from the production of the chemical needs to be lower than a specified amount. If the organic chemical is entirely or partially produced from renewable feedstocks, the entire life-cycle emissions need to be lower than those deriving from using the equivalent fossil resource.

The lack of a full criteria-based framework for transitional activities is criticised by many stakeholders as unsatisfactory in terms of sustainability ambitions and in leaving uncertainty to investors. This is also relevant for investors and producers of bio-based materials and products. Higher sustainability ambition levels and more specific criteria could favour fully bio-based materials and products over other activities that are truly transitional, thus not part of the final list of activities supported in a full circular economy.

Most criticism on the framework is on the inclusion or exclusion of nuclear energy and natural gas. A political compromise was reached that neither of the two are explicitly included or excluded from the list of transitional activities. The decision on inclusion or exclusion will be carried out by the EC in the detailed rules with technical input from a multi-stakeholder platform. It was agreed that all technologies will be assessed based on life cycle considerations, as well as in accordance with the additional requirements that apply to transition activities, and appropriate technical screening criteria will be developed including to avoid 'significant harm', including with regards to the disposal of waste.

Other specific comments on the framework include: i) the condition to determine whether a transitional activity does not hamper the development and deployment of low-carbon alternatives is difficult to prove, ii) as there is no time limit provided for the presence of transitional activities in the EU Taxonomy, its presence may risk slowing down development of

fully sustainable innovations, iii) the Taxonomy focuses mainly on environmental and economic sustainability, but should also include other ESG requirements such as social sustainability aspects. Providing more clarity on items i) and ii) would provide more certainty to the business case for bio-based materials and products and therefore help investors and producers to optimise their investment and production strategies.

A basis for addressing comment iii) is found in the Final Report on Social Taxonomy published by the Platform on Sustainable Finance in February 2022 (European Commission, 2022g). The report proposes a structure for an EU social taxonomy in line with the current legislative environment on sustainable finance and governance.⁵ It also recognises the importance of integrating the Environmental and Social Taxonomy and proposes concrete ways of achieving this. For instance, an option would be to make the environmental and social "do no significant harm" criteria valid for both the social and environmental part of all activities.

5.3 Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive

On 5 January 2023, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) entered into force. The goal of the legislation is to help investors, consumers, and other stakeholders evaluate the sustainability performance of EU-based companies, as well as related risks and opportunities. The CSRD requires all large companies and all listed companies to report on the environmental and social impact of their business activities, and on the business impact of their environmental, social and governance (ESG) efforts and initiatives.

The CSRD was introduced as a revision of the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), addressing several shortcomings identified by the European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) (source report). The identified issues included an insufficient disclosure of sustainability information, a lack of comparability in reporting, and limited reliability of the reported information. Given the limited effectiveness of the NFRD, a more robust reporting framework and auditing measures were necessary.

The CSRD was developed to expand the scope, sustainability disclosures and reporting requirements of the NFRD. It modernises and strengthens the rules concerning sustainability reporting and broadens the group of companies that are obliged to report. The updated rules will be applied to companies as of the 2024 financial year, for reports that will be published in 2025. Companies will have to report using the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), that were adopted by the EC on 31 July 2023. The ESRS provide a framework for companies to know what they need to report and how to do it to meet the CSRD requirements.

⁵ The suggested structure of a social taxonomy consists of three objectives: decent work (including for value-chain workers), adequate living standards and wellbeing for end-users, and inclusive and sustainable communities and societies.

The ESRS adopt a “double materiality” perspective, as they oblige companies to report on both their impacts on people and the environment, and on how social and environmental issues create financial risks and opportunities for the company. There are 12 ESRS, that cover a wide range of sustainability issues. ESRS1 and 2 are cross-cutting and apply to all companies, while the others are divided by topic and only applicable if relevant for the company’s business model and activity (Figure 2). To select which ESRS are relevant for them, companies conduct a “materiality assessment”, which identifies the most significant economic, environmental, and social impacts of an organization. Clearer science-based guidelines on how to conduct the materiality assessment, including a step-by-step methodology, would guarantee that companies actually report on all the relevant ESRS.

Figure 2. The 12 European Sustainability Reporting Standards divided by topic. Top ones (cross-cutting) apply to all entities, the other ones are subject to materiality assessment.

Companies involved in the production of bio-based materials and products can also be subject to the CSRD and will need to report on relevant ESRS. Circularity is particularly relevant, as bio-based products can be derived from renewable resources and minimise dependence on finite fossil fuels.

The General Disclosures (ESRS 2) already address circularity as they require companies to disclose information on how they identify and assess circular economy-related risks and opportunities throughout their value chain. The emphasis on circularity is further reinforced by ESRS E5, which focuses on resource use and the overall company alignment with circular economy practices. In particular, companies need to disclose their impacts on resource use and how they prevent or mitigate the negative effects. They also need to disclose their potential to adapt and align with circular economy principles. Finally, companies need to report the risks and opportunities related to resource use and circular economy, as well as their anticipated financial impacts.

The explicit focus of ESRS E5 on resource inflows and outflows makes it particularly relevant for bio-based materials and products. Specifically, companies are required to share detailed information on their policies for handling circular economy-related risks, opportunities, and impacts throughout their entire production process. Regarding resource inflows, companies need to disclose specifics such as weight and composition of technical and biological materials used in bio-based products. For resource outflows, they need to divulge their waste management strategies, efforts towards recycling, and overall practices aimed at reducing environmental impact.

Although companies are required to provide extensive information on resource use, the framework would benefit from a more science-based approach. This would guide companies to better determine the impact they have related to the use of resources and provide a standardised and uniform way to measure these impacts. The approach should adopt a life-cycle perspective, assessing upstream and downstream impacts and incorporating the use of renewable and non-renewable resources.

A shortcoming is that the definition of circular economy (objective 3) primarily focuses on recycling and reduction of waste but does not explicitly mention minimising resource use. There is also no mention of the different circular strategies that were defined in the EC's document "Categorisation system for the circular economy"; the document ranks different strategies to increase circularity (refuse, rethink, reduce, re-use, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, and recycle). In line with this, companies could be required to define which strategies they are adopting and how their actions contribute to that.

Although ESRS E5 is of particular importance for companies involved in the production of bio-based products, other ESRS can also apply. In particular, climate change (E1) and pollution (E2) can be very relevant. ESRS E1 requires companies to disclose information on their efforts to limit global warming to 1.5°C, in line with the objectives of the Paris Agreement. This includes reporting on energy use, greenhouse gas emissions, and water usage, enabling stakeholders to assess and compare the environmental sustainability of various bio-based production processes. ESRS E2 focuses on how companies contribute to pollution of water, air and soil, and which actions they take to prevent these impacts.

Better integration with the EU taxonomy is an aspect that should be taken into account to improve the effectiveness of environmental reporting in the EU. Both ESRS E1 and ESRS E2 explicitly mention the EU taxonomy, but only ESRS E1 requires companies to disclose information on how they plan to align with it. The same requirement could be added to the other environmental ESRS (E3-E5). It would also be beneficial to require companies to include detailed explanations on why some ESRS were excluded from the reporting. This is especially true for ESRS E1 (climate change), since all the actors need to reach or facilitate reaching net zero-emissions.

6 The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability

Another important area where EU regulation and policies are resulting in a positive stimulant to the market for bio-based polymers is the production and use of chemicals. The EU already had a comprehensive regulatory framework for chemicals for two decades when, in 2020, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability was published (European Commission (2020a)). This strategy defined an explicit aim to boost innovation in industry for safe and sustainable-by-design chemicals, including sustainable bio-based chemicals.

The Chemicals Strategy outlines more than 80 actions, and progress towards their implementation is actively monitored and published. Two of the more prominent actions are the strengthening of the existing cornerstone regulations for regulating chemicals, the Regulation on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and the legislation on hazard classification, labelling and packaging of chemicals (CLP).

6.1 Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)

The REACH regulation provides for the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemical substances. The main goal of REACH is to protect humans and the environment from potential harmful effects posed by chemicals. Under REACH, companies need to register and provide detailed information on the properties and uses of chemical substances they manufacture or import. The REACH regulation first entered into force in the EU in 2007 and has since been updated to reflect the advancements made in the chemical industry (European Commission, 2023e). The regulation covers all chemical substances made or sold in the EU in quantities above one tonne per year. Other jurisdictions such as China and the UK have also enacted REACH regulations, which share a similar purpose but differ in data collection and reporting requirements.

The regulation does not differentiate between bio-based and fossil-based chemicals; however, some REACH registration exemptions can typically be applied to bio-based production. Some substances (e.g. D-glucitol, ascorbic acid, glucose, as described in Annex IV of REACH regulation) and groups (e.g. natural chemicals, as described in Annex V of REACH) are regarded as safe and therefore excluded from registration. Even though these chemicals are not explicitly referred to as bio-based, in most cases they can be. Still, many companies dealing with bio-based products struggle to understand when and how they need to apply REACH regulations (Luit et al, 2016). More explicit reference to bio-based products would help bio-based companies to better understand the implications that REACH has for them.

Substances recovered from waste streams can also be exempted from registration if the original substance has already been registered, provided that the identity is proven. This poses a challenge

for companies, because substance identification can be difficult for many recovered materials and information often gets lost along the supply chain. This might discourage the recycling of specific waste streams and ultimately hamper the circular economy. In this context, sustainability certification could become a useful instrument, since it enhances traceability along the supply chain. Companies could use it to prove origin, content, and overall compliance with sustainability requirements of (certified) waste and be exempted from REACH registration.

Polymers, the building blocks of plastics, are currently not subject to the REACH regulation. Although monomers are included and need to be registered, the polymerization process can result in variations in molecular weight, structure, and reactivity. Including polymers would strengthen the effectiveness of REACH. Article 138(2) foresees a possible further review to extend the registration requirements to polymers, and the EC is working on a proposal to include certain polymers of concern.

As in the case for natural chemicals, natural polymers would be exempted from the regulation. The European Chemical Agency (ECHA) defines polymers as natural when the polymerisation takes place in nature as opposed to an industrial process, even if the process is the same and results in the same polymer. Biopolymers created with an industrial process, for instance industrial synthesis or fermentation, are therefore not considered to be natural. This means that most bio-based polymers, intended to be an alternative for fossil-based ones such as polypropylene (PP) or polyethylene terephthalate (PET), do not fall under the definition of natural polymers.

Some stakeholders from the bioplastics industry, such as Europe Bioplastics⁶, raised concerns regarding the definition of natural polymers adopted by ECHA. They fear that not including industrially synthesised biopolymers in the definition of natural polymers might slow down innovation in the field and overall progress towards EU sustainability goals. Their main argument is that when biopolymers are nature-identical, they should be treated as such. Moreover, the risks posed by biopolymers do not change based on whether the polymerisation happens in nature or not. Removing this distinction would also be in line with EC's proposal for the new Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation and other EU legislation.

While REACH safeguards environmental and human health through its focus on chemical safety, a gap exists in its consideration of broader sustainability dimensions. The regulation offers companies the possibility to include a socio-economic analysis when applying for registration of substances. However, the analysis only focuses on issues directly related to chemical safety for humans and the environment. Bio-based products can offer numerous sustainability gains when compared to fossil-based alternatives other than safety. It would be beneficial to offer companies the chance to weigh these aspects together with safety considerations when conducting a

⁶ European Bioplastics is a European association representing the interests of the bioplastics industry. See <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/>

socio-economic analysis. This would stimulate companies not only to search for safer alternatives, but also to include sustainability and circularity in their product design.

A recent study for the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water management (Hekman et al, 2023) concluded that the regulatory framework that regulates chemical substances and mixtures could use new and/or more targeted policy instruments to better encourage innovation. They conclude that while there are many novel chemical innovations developed in both academic and commercial settings, the information on hazard properties of these novelties is often incomplete and that this leads to innovations being placed on the market that could still be hazardous. They furthermore conclude that firms on average see more obstacles than drivers to engage in safe chemical innovation, and that there is scope to improve policies to better encourage safe chemical innovation. The analysis focuses on three types of policies and concluded:

1. When implementing a grant/subsidy scheme this is best done on a targeted basis, focusing on safe chemical innovation that engages the entire supply chain. The study concludes that in this way it promotes not only fundamental research and development (R&D) but can help in market uptake and thereby increasing economies of scale.
2. That a tax on the use of hazardous substances functions best for products with a high elasticity of demand and that such taxes have a higher short-term effectiveness for products/services which already have alternatives on the market, but which are not yet price competitive.
3. That ecolabels and information campaigns to increase public awareness on the hazards of product constituents can be a driver for innovation, but the effect of isolated campaigns is small.

6.2 Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Chemicals (CLP)

Whilst the REACH regulation allows people to determine and limit the hazardous risks posed by chemical substances, the CLP regulation ensures that the substances are properly packaged and the risks and safety information are thoroughly communicated. CLP entered into force on 20 January 2009 and introduced the United Nations globally harmonized system (UN GHS) for classification and labelling of chemicals into Europe. Under CLP, manufacturers, importers or downstream users of substances or mixtures need to classify, label and package their hazardous chemicals appropriately before placing them on the market.

As with REACH, CLP does not distinguish between bio- and fossil-based substances. It also applies to chemicals exempted from registration under REACH, even if treated in quantities below one tonne per year. Although the same obligations apply for both bio-based and traditional chemicals, companies dealing with bio-based products might encounter more difficulties when complying

with the regulations. For instance, a chemical should not be persistent, bioaccumulative⁷ and/or toxic. To demonstrate this, companies need to conduct a self-classification assessment which requires information on the environmental fate of the substance. This type of information can be hard to gather for newly developed chemicals, including bio-based ones.

Bio-based products also come with challenges specific to their nature. Current CLP regulations mostly cover risks for human safety, leaving environmental aspects aside. Specialised classification criteria that encompass risks typical of bio-based products, including, for example, the origin of materials, could improve the effectiveness of CLP for bio-based chemicals. ECHA found that almost half of the safety assessments conducted by companies are incomplete, mostly because information gets lost along the supply chain (ECHA, 2021).

Same as for REACH, the use of certification could play a role in facilitating communication along the supply chain. This would be especially beneficial to increase the traceability of products and ensure that information does not get lost when the substance passes from one supply chain element to the other. Moreover, sustainability aspects of the substances would be made available. This could be used to enhance the CLP labelling requirements to explicitly communicate the sustainability of chemicals. Bio-based materials could be advantaged because of their more sustainable and renewable nature compared to fossil alternatives. This measure would ultimately help consumers and businesses to make informed choices based on both safety and sustainability considerations.

⁷ Bioaccumulation is used to describe the increase in concentration of a substance, such as pesticides or other chemicals, in an organism over time.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the analysis in this report, the CHAMPION project has defined some recommendations for further detailing of proposed regulations.

Recommendation 1: Define minimum sustainability targets that are legally enshrined and sector-specific

Recent EU initiatives such as the mandatory sustainability reporting, as required in the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the harmonisation of reporting criteria in the EU Taxonomy, provide more transparency in sustainability reporting. Yet, they still rely on voluntary action and do not create a level playing field among companies. Moreover, whereas the requirements do provide positive stimulation, the incentive for real action is limited. To support such real action, it is recommended to define minimum sustainability targets that are legally enshrined. This provides certainty, both in terms of actual improvements and equal treatment. Companies can then voluntarily set additional targets, compare these against the minimum targets and report their progress accordingly.

Definition of targets could start with formulation of decarbonisation targets, and in later stage could be expanded to other environmental goals such as biodiversity, water quality and air pollution. For decarbonisation targets, where possible, these should be based on science-based targets that are set in line with sectoral decarbonisation pathways. In this respect, it is important to be flexible in the understanding of sustainability. As methods to measure and communicate the pillars of sustainability evolve (e.g. the Planetary Boundaries model), policies should recognise this greater objectivity and consider revising targets to ensure our ambitions equate with favourable (sustainable) outcomes.

It is furthermore recommended to differentiate stringency by sector and by size of the company to ensure ambitions are in line with relative capacity as well as to ensure cost-effectiveness of target achievement.

Recommendation 2: formulation of targets and ecodesign requirements should be incremental, achievable and with a longer-term horizon

The current policy approach to stimulate sustainable transition and circularity centres around ecodesign requirements. As explained in this report, the proposed ESPR is based on the 2009 Ecodesign Directive and will take this a step further by strengthening the requirements and including additional product groups. That approach is recommended to be taken forward by adding a longer-term horizon as well as a clear signal that further expansion and strengthening will be taking place in the coming years. This is recommended for both target setting and the ecodesign requirements so that the combination will effectively support innovation and provide a good business case for the market for sustainable products. It will help companies to gradually adapt their production processes and meet all targets and requirements in a cost-effective manner.

Recommendation 3: when defining targets and ecodesign requirements take a wider geographic perspective

From a corporate perspective, targets and ecodesign requirements would ideally be set at global level to protect competitiveness of companies and avoid production shift. Recognising that achieving global agreements may be challenging, the recommendation is to define such targets and ecodesign requirements at minimum at the European level. This could be complemented by additional requirements such as imposing ecodesign requirements not only on products made in the EU, but to all products sold on the EU market, similar to the requirements in REACH. Another option would be to introduce a border tax for imported products that do not meet EU ecodesign requirements. This could build on current experience in the context of the EU carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM). Lessons learned could be taken forward to other sustainability requirements and a mechanism implemented to demonstrate compliance with requirements, ensured by use of validated certificates.

Recommendation 4: formulate mandatory ecodesign requirements for specific products

Options for product deconstruction to the molecular level vary per sector and per type. CHAMPION aims to achieve such levels of deconstruction, at the highest level of sustainability, without the need for chemical recycling and avoiding use of fossil fuels for mechanical recycling. Where such options for sustainable deconstruction down to molecular level are proven and near-commercially available, it is recommended to define mandatory ecodesign requirements and thus stimulate the market for biopolymers.

Recommendation 5: define more specific quality standards to support sustainability

The EU has formulated several types of standards to support sustainability, including standards for industrial composting and biodegradation and standards for recycled plastics. To support the market for biopolymers it is recommended to develop and/or improve quality standards for sorted waste and recycled products, or more generally for bio-based and recycled polymers, to address concerns regarding quality and continuity of supply of reused products and recycled products. In addition, existing standards at material level should be adapted to component level, where possible, or additional standards should be developed to that end. Having such more tailored standards available would likely trigger development of quality labels and as such help inform consumers and improve sustainability reporting.

Recommendation 6: improve the definition of circular economy in corporate sustainability reporting and require reporting in line with targets and standards

The EU is making important steps forward in directing consumption towards higher sustainability, including by setting requirements for corporate sustainability reporting and formulating a classification system that defines sustainability criteria. In these requirements and criteria, it is recommended to improve the definition of circular economy. Where the current definition focuses on recycling and reduction of waste, it is recommended to include other aspects of achieving sustainability such as minimising resource use. In addition, it would help to require

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companies to explicitly define their (preferably science-based) targets and strategies as well as to report progress against these.

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